

DEMOCRATIZATION IN THE DIGITAL AGE: AN ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL MEDIA'S IMPACT ON DEMOCRACIES IN PAKISTAN (2018-2024)

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Abstract

The digital age has had a significant impact on democracy. It has brought revolution in world politics. The rise of digital age has changed how democracies work. Digital tools have made it easier for people to get involved in democracy. They can now contact elected leaders more easily and join political discussions through social media. It has also increased political participation, political awareness and public opinions. Overall, the digital era has transformed the landscape of democratic structures, presenting both opportunities and challenges for the preservation and evolution of democratic principles. However, the digital age has also offered both opportunities and challenges for democracy. This study highlights the deep impact of social media on democratization in Pakistan, particularly from 2018 to 2024. Furthermore, this study also examines how social media has improved access to information. It explores how these platforms shape public opinion and encourage more participation in democracy. Social media helps make governments and organizations more open and answerable to the people. The research adopts a mixed-methods approach, utilizing both qualitative and quantitative data to explore the complex role of social media in shaping democratic discourse in Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

The digital age has brought about major changes in nearly every part of daily life in the 21st century. Today, virtualization and digital tools are reshaping how people live, work, and connect across different areas like government, society, culture, economy, politics, and religion (Hussain & Qureshi, 2018). These shifts happen quickly and affect everyone, making life more interconnected and dependent on digital systems. As a result, human experiences and

community interactions are changing in profound ways. Likewise, advancements in ICT have also brought significant changes to democracy. Easier communication now links communities and countries around the world. Sharing ideas and opinions has become simpler, and accessing information is no longer difficult (Zaheer, 2018). These changes have made democratic processes more open and accessible than before. While, in the past,

democracy relied on traditional ways that often made it hard for people to access information about state and government affairs. Communicating ideas or sharing opinions was also a struggle for many. These methods limited people's ability to stay informed or participate fully in political discussions (Heller, 2022). That why, the old systems in democratic countries were complex, which kept public participation in democracy squat and people found it hard to get involved due to these difficulties. While, advances in information and communication technology have changed this. New tools have made democracy more accessible and brought many useful benefits. Democracy in the digital world makes it easier for communities to access and share information (Persily, 2020). Yet, while there are many benefits, digital democracy also has drawbacks. Negative effects are also linked to increased online engagement and the rush to share information quickly. The misuse of online platforms as tools for community participation is common. A vital aspect of democracy today is that all internet users must be aware of their ethics and manners when sharing their opinions. Proper behavior and respect in online discussions are essential to maintaining a healthy digital community (Khan, Rafique, & Nasim, 2023). Digital democracy is heavily influenced by virtual space, particularly social media. Because, social media represents a key part of virtual space. In this context, providing access to the internet is the most important issue. Social media can offer many important benefits for democratic life. When people use social media to take part in civic discussions and decision-making, it helps to realize the true goal of digital democracy. In this modern era, people can easily access information and share their goals through social media platforms like Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, TikTok, as well as blogs and various other websites (Shafeeq, 2022). This easy access makes it simple to share opinions, gather information, and bring people together for important causes in a democracy.

Social media has significantly impacted Pakistani politics. Between 2018 and 2024, Pakistan saw big changes in how people use online platforms for democracy. Social media sites like Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram let politicians talk directly to the public. This way, they don't have to rely on traditional

media outlets. Instead, they can share their messages straight with their supporters. It has made it easier for politicians to connect and communicate without middlemen. Social media opened up new ways for people to share their views and talk openly about politics. These platforms influenced how people view political issues. They encouraged more active participation from citizens. Additionally, online discussions became livelier and more widespread (Khan, Rafique, & Nasim, 2023). These platforms also influence how they interact with politicians and take part in elections. In Pakistan, political parties now rely heavily on social media to reach voters. These deviations have the possible to make democracy work healthier (Jamil, 2024). Hence, there are usually two main issues about how media and politics relate during democratization. One is about how the media helps create democracy. The other worries about how media can become more democratic itself. It is challenging to establish a clear cause-and-effect relationship between media and the advancement of democracy. The evidence available is largely anecdotal and cannot be rigorously tested with data (Beaufort, 2018). Media can be viewed as a reflection of society, shaping its ideas and values, or as a force that actively drives change. Similarly, the freedom of the press is sometimes perceived as an indication that democracy is strengthening, while at other times it is regarded as a prerequisite for democracy to function effectively. Both media and democracy experts perceive mass media as one of the most significant democratic instruments (Kang & Konietzky, 2022). They assert that it plays a crucial role in enhancing electoral processes, fortifying political parties, and improving the efficacy of parliament, courts, and other state institutions. Even civil society benefits from a robust media system, which aids in safeguarding and promoting democratic values and practices (Mahaswa, 2017).

1.1 Research Questions

RQ#1: What influence does social media have on democratic participation and political engagement in Pakistan, especially among young people?

RQ#2: How does social media influence public opinion to enhance the process of democratisation in Pakistan?

2. Digital Revolution and Its Impacts on Democratic Processes in Pakistan (2018-2024)

Democracy is a widely accepted form of government around the world. Over 165 countries have adopted democratic systems, showing their global popularity. Looking at Pakistan's history, since it was created in 1947, the country has never established a fully stable democracy. Military interventions have repeatedly hurt the democratic system (Akram, Ahmed, & Azhar, 2024). Since 2010, social media has become a major part of Pakistani politics. It quickly gained popularity among politicians, the media, and everyday people. The influence of social media has grown a lot, especially in recent years. Several events since 2005 show how social platforms are increasingly central to political discussions and debates. (Heller, 2022).

Social media first appeared in Pakistan in 1995. Today, Pakistan ranks sixth among South Asian countries and 27th worldwide in internet use. The country has a large youth population, with around 67% of people under 30. Among young people, Facebook and Twitter are the most popular social media platforms. These apps are widely used and hold a strong place in the lives of Pakistan's youth. Pakistan has a high internet penetration rate of 15.9%, with over 44.6 million users online. Social media is changing how people communicate and has become a powerful tool in politics worldwide. In Pakistani politics, social media's potential was first seen by former President Pervez Musharraf. His online presence gained huge public attention, with 454,016 likes. Since 2013, all major political parties PPP, PML-N, and PTI have set up social media teams. These groups work alongside the personal social media accounts of party leaders. Their goal is to promote the party's views, share their ideas, and support their candidates. The social media cells help them reach voters and spread their messages effectively. This effort is a key part of how parties communicate in today's politics. Some argue that political parties used their media teams to spread negative rumours about their opponents. Despite these issues, it is clear that voter turnout reached 60% in the 2018 and 52.1% in the 2024 general elections (Jamil, 2024). Pakistan's push into digital technology is reshaping its economy, society, and government. The government has launched several initiatives to promote this shift. One

example is the Digital Pakistan Policy 2018, which aims to support the use of technology for economic and social benefits while boosting investments in the IT sector. Over the past four years, internet usage has surged from just 2% to 30%, removing numerous hurdles and opening up new avenues for growth. The government is investing in training programs that focus on technical and vocational education. These programs aim to equip the large youth population with new skills to secure better employment. Through this initiative, they intend to provide young people with more opportunities and enhance their prospects. The goal is to prepare young workers with practical skills they can utilize immediately. This effort is part of a broader plan to develop a stronger, more skilled workforce (Jamil, 2024). The government is placing greater emphasis on utilizing digital tools in policies and administration. This encompasses electronic voting machines and a digital census. Such services can enhance the speed and efficiency of government operations. They can also contribute to reducing corruption and simplifying life for citizens (Khan, Rafique, & Nasim, 2023). New technologies affect the functioning of democracy. As digital tools become more common, democratic systems around the world are changing significantly. These changes open up many new ways for people to get involved and contribute. They also create fresh chances for growth and development within communities. At the same time, new challenges arise that need quick and clear solutions (Sadiq, Zain, & Ajis, 2018).

However, during elections 2018 and 2024 elections, social media was very important. It gave political parties a way to connect with voters and influence public opinion. PTI and PML-N used Facebook and Twitter a lot to bridge the gap between the people and their parties. Social media became a constant platform for campaigning and spreading messages. These sites are used by PML-N and PTI to set agendas and rally support (Masood & Adnan, 2021). Social media helps make information more accessible to everyone. However, it also brings up tricky moral, legal, and cultural questions. False information spread by opponents damages the fairness of elections and shifts public trust. Online ads raise worries about how personal data is used and kept private. To ensure elections are fair and democratic, governments and

civil groups must step up and take their share of responsibility. Using social media effectively can help, but only if these groups actively work to protect the process and people's rights (Shabbir & Haider, 2023).

1.2 Research Methodology

This study used an analytical as well as descriptive approach to examine how social media influences democracies in Pakistan from 2018 to 2024. The main objective of the proposed research is to understand how social media usage affects people participation in democratic processes. The research involved collecting data through a survey. A clear and structured questionnaire was created to gather details on social media use, political engagement, and youth engagement on democracy. A survey was conducted online, which gave participants the chance to share their views and experiences openly. To choose who took part, a purposive sampling method was used, focusing mainly on young people. Because the Pakistani youth are seen as the most active users of social media. They are heavily affected by social networks when it comes to learning about politics. Young people often participate and stay informed through these online platforms. Their frequent activity makes them key players in political discussions online. This method made sure the sample included people who are active on social media and care about politics and democracy. This study uses a detailed research method to explore how social media affects democracy in Pakistan. The approach helps uncover important details about the influence of online platforms. It offers clear insights into how social

media shapes democratic processes in the country. By focusing on solid research techniques, the study presents accurate findings.

3. Population and Sample Size

The researchers gathered survey data from 51 respondents within Pakistan's general population. This group includes Pakistani citizens eligible to participate in elections, such as voters, activists, and those interested in politics. The population studied is highly diverse, encompassing people of different ages, backgrounds, and areas. For this research, purposive sampling was employed. Fifty-one responses were obtained from individuals across a range of age groups. This method facilitated the collection of a broad array of opinions on how social media influences democracy in Pakistan. This sample size is suitable for an initial study aimed at exploring the relationship between social media and democracy.

4. Data Analysis

The data was examined through thematic analysis to identify patterns, trends, and connections between social media and democracies in Pakistan from 2018 to 2024. Four main themes, social media's landscape, Social Media's role, democratic participation and public opinion by social media, emerged from the survey data. The themes were identified after reviewing the data collected during the survey. The researchers utilized SPSS, a widely used statistical software, to analyze the results. This helped them find important links between different variables.

4.1 Results and Discussions

4.1.1 Section (A): Demographic Information

Table 1: Respondents' Age

Age		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-25	28	54.9	54.9	54.9
	25-30	10	19.6	19.6	74.5
	30-35	7	13.7	13.7	88.2
	35-above	6	11.8	11.8	100.0
Total		51	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Respondents' Gender

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	31	60.8	60.8	60.8
	Male	20	39.2	39.2	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Respondents' Education

Educational Level					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Graduation	18	35.3	35.3	35.3
	Other	5	9.8	9.8	45.1
	Post-Graduation	21	41.2	41.2	86.3
	Under Graduation	7	13.7	13.7	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Respondents' Occupation

51 responses

4.1.2 Section (B): Social Media Usage
Social Media's Landscape in Pakistan

There were 71.70 million social media users in January 2023, making up 30.1% of the total population. This number is expected to grow, with projections showing around 85 to 90 million users by 2025. At the start of 2023, Pakistan had 87.35 million internet users. This meant that about 36.7% of the population was online. Mobile connections were much higher, with 191.8 million active cellular lines. This number equals roughly 80.5% of the country's population. In early 2023, Facebook had around 37.30 million users in Pakistan, mostly adults aged 18 and older. Meanwhile, Instagram had about 18.8 million users in early 2025. Its popularity is rising among younger people. In early 2023, YouTube had 71.7 million users in Pakistan, making it a huge

platform for content creators. Meanwhile, LinkedIn had 9.3 million members in Pakistan at that time. By early 2025, LinkedIn's membership had grown to 15 million, offering a strong space for professional networking (Khan, Naz, Ali, & Ali, 2022). Pakistan's mobile internet subscriptions are expected to grow by 10-12% each year. By 2025, the number could reach over 140 million broadband users. This steady rise reflects increasing demand for mobile internet services across the country. These figures illustrate the significant growth in internet and mobile phone usage in Pakistan recently. Millions of people in Pakistan rely heavily on social media platforms such as Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, and Facebook. People use these sites every day to chat, read news, and take part in public discussions. Millions of Pakistanis go online often because smartphones are easy to get, and mobile

data is affordable. Over 60% of young people in Pakistan are active on social media. They use these platforms to hold the government accountable and to spread awareness about social issues. These reasons have helped social media use grow quickly across the country. The number of social media users in Pakistan stayed around 71.70 million from 2023 to 2024. As the population grows and internet access spreads, this number could rise significantly. By 2030, social media

users might reach between 80 and 100 million (Khan, Rafique, & Nasim, 2023). This study shows that most people in Pakistan use social media and see it as a key part of modern culture. The sample surveyed reveals that 35.3% agree with this view, while 56.9% strongly agree. Many are interested in using platforms like Instagram, Twitter and Facebook to follow daily political news.

Table 5: Social Media in Pakistani Culture

Do you think Social Media has become an integral part of Pakistani culture?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	18	35.3	35.3	35.3
	Disagree	3	5.9	5.9	41.2
	Neutral	1	2.0	2.0	43.1
	Strongly Agree	29	56.9	56.9	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

The study showed that 32.9% of participants agreed, while 28.1% strongly agreed, that they use social media platforms like Instagram, Twitter and Facebook to share their political views. About 17.6% of

respondents expressed interest in using Facebook for this purpose. Meanwhile, 27.0% are active on Instagram, and 29.4% use Twitter to like, share and comment on political content.

Table 6: Social Media Platforms

Which Social Media platforms do you use most frequently?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Facebook	9	17.6	17.6	17.6
	Facebook, Instagram	3	5.9	5.9	23.5
	Facebook, Twitter, Instagram	4	7.8	7.8	31.4
	Facebook, Twitter, Other	1	2.0	2.0	33.3
	Instagram	16	31.4	31.4	64.7
	Instagram, Other	2	3.9	3.9	68.6
	Other	6	11.8	11.8	80.4
	Twitter	8	15.7	15.7	96.1
	Twitter, Instagram	2	3.9	3.9	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

4.1.3 Section (C): Democratization and Social Media

4.1.3.1 Role of Social Media in Democratisation

Democratization is the process of establishing a democracy following the end of non-democratic rule. It primarily involves transitioning from one form of government to another. A democracy is considered robust when it conducts free and fair elections,

prevents monopolies of power, and safeguards the rights of its citizens (Huber & Strauss, 2018). The relationship between parliament and democracy resembles a collaboration among various groups (Yasin & Batool, 2020). These groups work together to ensure the smooth development of democracy, supporting one another as they advance on the path to democracy. Democratization aims to prevent any

regime that infringes upon citizens' rights, while also striving to eliminate all forms of non-democratic governance. Numerous countries are still striving to establish genuine democratic systems. However, several factors influence whether this process succeeds or fails (Cheema & Hashmi, 2021). Social media encompasses various online platforms designed for communication, allowing users to readily share ideas and information. Individuals utilize these sites to join communities, exchange knowledge, and connect with others. It serves as a versatile tool that helps users maintain contact, collaborate, and share experiences across different networks. (R. Ahmad, 2002). Social media can be perceived as a system that collects and disseminates communications based on the numerous meetings and thoughts individuals have online. Today, notable examples of social media platforms include Facebook, Twitter, interest groups, and LinkedIn. These platforms permit users to share their thoughts, ideas, pictures, and videos with friends and family. Primarily, social media functions as a space for individuals to express themselves, learn new things, and engage in conversations. Social media offers users greater freedom to convey their thoughts. It played a vital role in the 2013 and 2018 elections in Pakistan. While political parties organized large rallies and face-to-face events, they also concentrated significantly on platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. These sites evolved into crucial spaces for campaigning and rapidly reaching voters. Social networking has become essential for maintaining connections with friends and family, helping

individuals strengthen personal relationships. Concurrently, many individuals utilize it for professional networking and job searching. Social media has now become an integral aspect of everyday life, both for personal and professional purposes. It facilitates connections with individuals who share similar interests, providing a platform for open idea sharing and free discussions on common topics. Thanks to social media and advancements in technology, the boundaries between people and cultures are increasingly blurred, fostering a sense of global connectivity. This makes it challenging to envision life without the pervasive influence of social media. Social media grants individuals a platform to share their opinions, engage in discussions, and access information. It empowers Pakistani citizens to participate in politics and stay informed (Khan, Naz, Ali, & Ali, 2022). Through these platforms, they can connect and articulate their ideas with ease. Social media is now a critical tool for political engagement in Pakistan. With 4.5 billion internet users and 3.8 billion social media users globally, its impact is irrefutable. It is crucial to explore the relationship between social media and democracy, as democracy remains a dominant system around the world. The study showed that a large majority, 66.7%, strongly agreed with the idea that social media has helped promote democracy in Pakistan from 2018 to 2024. An additional 25.5% of participants also agreed that social media has influenced their political views and helped raise awareness. Only 7.8% of those surveyed disagreed with this statement.

Table 7: Democratization and Social Media

Do you think social media has contributed to the democratization process in Pakistan from 2018 to 2024?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	34	66.7	66.7	66.7
	Disagree	4	7.8	7.8	74.5
	Strongly Agree	13	25.5	25.5	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

4.1.3.2 Youth Engagement in the Process of Democratisation during Elections 2018-2024

Social media is playing an increasingly significant role in political awareness in Pakistan, especially among young people. Today, about 3.5 billion people are using social media platforms worldwide. That's

approximately 45% of the total population. While, this figure keeps growing day by day. However, it indicates that social media has become indispensable for raising awareness and spreading information in Pakistan. In 2020, Pakistan had about 76.38 million people using the internet. Out of these, 37 million

actively used social media platforms. In recent years, more young people in Pakistan have become interested in politics. Their participation was clear during the 2018 and 2024 elections. In 2018, only 37% of young voters went to the polls, indicating that youth participation was still low. However, their desire to engage in politics is increasing. More young people are paying attention to election news than before. Youth participation in politics is rising in Pakistan, reflecting a changing attitude towards democracy. In the 2024 elections, more young voters cast their ballots than ever before. Voter turnout reached 48%, which is 11 points higher than in 2018. This increase demonstrates that efforts to engage young people are effective. Programs aimed at giving them a voice in democracy are making a tangible difference. Groups

like the Pakistan Institute of Legislative Development and Transparency (PILDAT) focus on improving civic knowledge and engagement among youth. They organize workshops, training sessions, and publish studies to educate young people about voting. These activities explain why voting matters and how elections function. Their main goal is to help youth recognize the importance of participating in elections. PILDAT's online campaign, "Awami Mukalma," reached approximately 8.85 million people, broadening knowledge about civic rights and responsibilities. The findings revealed that 41.2% strongly agreed, while 52.9% agreed, that social media used more effectively to progress youth engagement in democratisation in Pakistan from 2018 to 2024.

Table 8: Youth Engagement on Social Media

Do you think social media can be used more effectively to improve youth engagement in democratisation in Pakistan from 2018 to 2024?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	27	52.9	52.9	52.9
	Disagree	3	5.9	5.9	58.8
	Strongly Agree	21	41.2	41.2	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

4.1.4 Section (D): Social Media and Democratic Participation

4.1.4.1 Social Media’s Impact on Political Participation

Political participation involves people engaging in various political events both in their country and worldwide. It means taking part in activities related to government and politics. This can include voting, protesting, or discussing political issues. It reflects a person's effort to influence decisions and policies. Being politically active helps shape the way a government runs and responds to people's needs. It is a key part of a healthy democracy where citizens have a voice. Overall, political participation is about being involved in the process that decides how a country is governed. Social media has been very important in shaping political participation in Pakistan's elections of 2018 and 2024. Sites like Facebook and Twitter gave people a way to get involved in democracy. Citizens could share their thoughts and give feedback on government policies in real time. Public

engagement was easier, giving people a way to share their opinions during the elections. In 2024, social media played a key role in shaping how voters saw candidates and issues. It became an important tool for influencing perceptions and spreading information quickly. Political parties and candidates used social media to share their messages and attract voters. As a result, social media helps bring greater fairness and transparency in democracies. Citizens can now express themselves and question leaders more easily. This shift has made it increasingly difficult for those in power to disregard public concerns. Social platforms enable people to act as watchdogs and advocate for change. More individuals are turning to platforms like Twitter to demand transparency, expose corruption, and critique government actions. For instance, in 2021, activist Alamgir Khan’s #FixIt campaign gained attention for highlighting Karachi’s inadequate infrastructure and sanitation challenges. His efforts demonstrated how social media activism can exert pressure on local officials to address

community issues. Viral videos on Facebook and Twitter played a significant role in disseminating the message (Batool, 2024). Today, social media platforms like Instagram, Twitter and Facebook have completely changed how people vote and run political campaigns. They allow campaigns to reach more people quickly and easily. Citizens now have new ways to take part in politics thanks to these platforms. Social media offers

fresh chances for everyone to become involved and have their voice heard. Data shows that 92.2% of respondents use social media to join online political discussions or debates. About 62.7% say they rarely take part in political actions aimed at boosting voting rates or making elections more transparent. Meanwhile, 41.2% say they never use social media to participate in online political conversations.

Table 9: Social Media and Political Participation

Have you ever participated in online political discussions or debates on social media?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	21	41.2	41.2	41.2
	Rarely	11	21.6	21.6	62.7
	Yes	15	29.4	29.4	92.2
	Yes Occasionally	4	7.8	7.8	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

Young people in our community often share their views on social media. When surveyed, over half of the respondents, 54.9%, said social media shapes

opinions. They noted that this influence is especially strong among youth. The survey covered political topics from the 2018 elections up to 2024 in Pakistan.

Table 10: Social Media and Public Opinion

Do you believe that Social Media has influenced public opinions, particularly among youth, on political issues from the 2018 elections to 2024?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	28	54.9	54.9	54.9
	Disagree	1	2.0	2.0	56.9
	Strongly Agree	22	43.1	43.1	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

4.1.4.2 Social Media’s Impact on Political Awareness

The use of social media for political awareness in Pakistan is growing fast, especially among young people. Around 15.1% of the country's population is Facebook users. According to global statistics from StatCounter, approximately 92% of social media users are in the world. Current data shows that 3.5 billion people, nearly 45% of the world’s population, use social media. In 2020, Pakistan had about 76.38 million internet users and 37 million who used social media. Among these users, 36 million were on Facebook, and around 1.26 million used Twitter. Approximately 41% of users are aged between 18 and 24, while 36% fall into the 25 to 34 age group. Young people in Pakistan are very active on social media.

They regularly participate in online political discussions to stay informed about politics. Today, in the age of social media, young people are more interactive and socially active. They are also more aware of politics through platforms like Facebook and Twitter. Social media has helped create a stronger public space where people can share and discuss ideas openly. The survey found that About 62.7% of respondents agree, while 23.5% strongly agree, that they have been informed about social media activities related to politics, like Facebook and Twitter and they learn about current politics between the government and the opposition through social media platforms like Twitter and Instagram.

Table 11: Social Media and Political Awareness

Do you agree social media influences your voting decision during the elections 2018 and 2024?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	32	62.7	62.7	62.7
	Disagree	7	13.7	13.7	76.5
	Strongly Agree	12	23.5	23.5	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

4.1.4.3 Social Media’s Impact on Public Opinion

Social media platforms play a key role in today’s politics. They shape how people think and affect voting and policy talks. These sites have changed how we discuss issues. They can sway elections and influence the way leaders debate and make decisions. Social media platforms now play a major role in politics. They give people a place to talk, share ideas, and argue about political topics like never before (Banger, 2024). As social media becomes more important in politics, understanding its effect on opinions is crucial. In democratic societies, public views used to be shaped mostly by news outlets, politicians, and face-to-face talks. Today, online interactions play a bigger role in forming political beliefs and ideas. This change greatly affects how democracy works today. Social media makes it easier for people to share information. At the same time, it

brings new problems like false news, echo chambers, and growing political divides. Social media played an important role in shaping public opinion during Pakistan’s elections in 2018 and 2024. It has greatly affected how people view politics in democracies, both for better and for worse. It has opened up new ways for people to get involved in politics and find information. But it has also led to increased political divide and the spread of false information. Many people now get stuck in echo chambers, which hurts honest discussion and debate. The future of democracy depends on how well societies can reduce social media's harmful effects while using it to boost democratic participation. The survey revealed that 64.7% of participants believe social media has a strong influence on shaping public opinion in Pakistan from 2018 to 2024. Meanwhile, 31.4% think it has a moderate impact.

Table 12: Social Media and Public Opinion

How much influence do you think social media has on shaping public opinion in Pakistan from 2018 to 2024?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	A great deal	33	64.7	64.7	64.7
	A little	1	2.0	2.0	66.7
	A moderate amount	16	31.4	31.4	98.0
	None at all	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

4.1.4.4 Transparency and Accountability

Social media serves as a clear tool for transparency and good governance. Its widespread use allows individuals and groups to share information about corruption and misconduct by politicians. This platform has the power to create the openness needed for accountability. When more people participate online, it becomes harder for corrupt actions to stay hidden. Social media helps keep leaders honest by making their wrongdoings visible to the public. This

transparency is essential for a society that demands fair and honest leadership. Democratic government relies on a key idea called political accountability. This means that the government is responsible to the people. In democracy, public power is used to serve the common good. It works hand in hand with good governance, which focuses on using power fairly and for everyone’s benefit. In democratic governments, political accountability means elected leaders are responsible to the people. They must follow the

constitution, act in the public's best interest, and provide essential services. This accountability ensures that officials remain answerable for their actions and decisions. It is a way to keep leaders honest and committed to serving the community. Ultimately, it helps protect democracy by making sure the government respects the rules and meets the needs of the citizens. According to the democratic view, accountability happens when parliament works properly and elections are free and fair. These conditions depend on respecting freedom of speech,

honest journalism, and giving citizens the chance to speak out. Citizens must also be able to take part in political discussions and decision-making. Without these elements, true accountability cannot be achieved. The survey found that About 49% of respondents agree, while 21.6% strongly agree, while 23.5% respondents were disagree regarding that social media has also increased transparency and accountability in Government during the elections of 2018 and 2024.

Table 13: Social Media’s Role on Transparency and Accountability

Do you agree that social media has also increased transparency and accountability in Government during the elections of 2018 and 2024?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	25	49.0	49.0	49.0
	Disagree	12	23.5	23.5	72.5
	Strongly Agree	11	21.6	21.6	94.1
	Strongly Disagree	3	5.9	5.9	100.0
	Total	51	100.0	100.0	

4.1.4.5 Challenges and Opportunities

This digital transformation has created new challenges and opportunities for politicians, journalists, political institutions, and the media to reconnect and engage with citizens. Research on social media in Pakistan from 2018 to 2024 shows a complicated link to democracy. The rapport isn't straightforward; social media both supports and challenges democratic development. It influences how people share ideas and spread news, shaping public opinion in many ways. Overall, its impact on democracy in Pakistan is complex and not easy to understand. It is neither all good nor all bad. It has changed how people interact with democracy and politics. Citizens can now share swift feedback on government policies and actions easily. This keeps people more informed and aware of what's happening. On one side if it encourages more political

discussions and active participation, and another side it can also carries solemn problems. False information spreading on social media weakens people's ability to develop and share their political views. It also blocks the open discussion of public ideas. When people see wrong or misleading facts, they might form or change their opinions without questioning what they believe. Often, these changes are based on false information or mistaken views of what others think. False information can spread quickly via social media, which intensifies conflicts and anger. Generally, social media has both good and bad effects on politics. At the same time, it makes it easy for false stories to go viral fast. This makes it harder for society to have honest debates and a clear understanding of important issues (Dumbrava, 2021). The following graph highlights the challenges that exist when using social media to promote democracy in Pakistan.

Conclusion

The digital age has opened new doors for democracy in Pakistan. Citizens now have more ways to connect with government and institutions than ever before. Between 2018 and 2024, the country saw many changes that could strengthen democratic practices. Social media has become a key part of political talk worldwide. It gives people a powerful way to voice opinions and create a livelier democracy. It has played a crucial role in raising political awareness among the youth. Their active participation through online platforms enhances democratic ideals and engagement. In recent years, political leaders in democracies have become more answerable for their actions. It helps young people in Pakistan to understand how the government works. The proposed study indicates that Pakistani youth are vigorously using social media to educate themselves about politics. They are well-informed about the impact of social media on democracies. However, they are participating especially in political debates and discussions. This trend boosts the process of democratization especially from 2018 to 2024 in Pakistan. Today, people are leveraging social media to learn about voting, political leaders, and political parties. This contributes to strengthening democracy in Pakistan. Research demonstrates that most young people utilize social media, which fortifies their political beliefs and opinions. It provides them with an opportunity to engage actively in politics and make their voices heard. Such interactions enhance their ability to learn and share opinions more actively. The study found that social media promotes

democracy in Pakistan. Its usage enhances engagement between people and the political system, thereby reinforcing democracy in Pakistan. The study illustrates that the positive utilization of social media can strengthen Pakistan’s democracy. It suggests that when used judiciously, social media can foster a healthier and more active democratic environment. It is also expected that social media will be a very imperative mediator of change in the near future in Pakistan.

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